

MINI FOOTBALL, PSYCHOLOGICAL TRAINING OF FOOTBALL
PLAYERS IN THE PRE-COMPETITION PERIOD

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Nurimov Zafar Rakhmonberdievich

Professor of the Department
Combat and physical training
Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Academy of the Republic of Uzbekistan
e-mail: akrom.mir1988@gmail.com

Abstract: The article examines the current state of the problem of special (pre-competitive) mental training of football players with the use of effective and extensive means and methods at all stages and periods of year-round training.

Keywords: mini-football, psychological preparation, pre-competition period, effectiveness of preparation.

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Football has been and remains the most popular sport in our country, but at the same time, according to scientific research, the productivity of children's sports institutions engaged in the training of young sports reserve of football players remains very low. The problem of developing the speed and strength training of young football players is one of the most significant at the early stage of sports specialization. It becomes the most important for the practice of education and development of a comprehensively developed personality, as it is directly related to the whole complex of problems of training a young football player in physical development, ball possession techniques and interaction with other players in the team.

In modern conditions of the development of sports, the importance of such human qualities as the ability to quickly navigate in space, subtly differentiate their muscle sensations and regulate the degree of muscle tension, quickly respond to environmental signals and it is advisable to act in changing conditions, which cannot be fully demonstrated without sufficiently developed speed and strength training. A lot of factual material accumulated on this problem in our country and abroad is presented in various publications that are not systematized, little-known and not implemented in the practice of coaches in various sports. Sets of exercises with an elastic band for the development of speed and strength training will be useful only if they are consistently and purposefully performed, repeated and variable repetition.

Competitive activity of a football player is characterized by the need to perform complex technical actions in conditions of time shortage and significant

physical and psychological stress. As an increase in the psychological stability of young football players, a wide variety of special exercises and methodological techniques can be considered.

During the preparation for specific competitions, a special (pre-competitive) mental preparation of an athlete for performance is provided, characterized by the desire for a mandatory victory, emotional excitement, resistance to the influence of internal and external interference, the ability to arbitrarily control actions, emotions and behavior, the ability to immediately perform actions necessary for victory during the performance.

An important component of psychological preparation for specific competitions is:

- awareness by young athletes of the importance of the upcoming game;
- informing players about the conditions of the game (time and place, presence of spectators, coverage of the playing field, illumination, etc.);
- identifying strengths and weaknesses in the opponents' game and preparing for the competition taking into account these features and their capabilities;
- instilling in students confidence in their abilities and capabilities to achieve a positive result;
- overcoming negative emotions caused by the upcoming game in young football players and creating an optimistic emotional state in the team.

The effectiveness of psychological training is achieved through the skillful use of extensive tools and methods that should be included in all stages and periods of year-round training.

Pre-competitive psychological training is aimed at creating the mobilization readiness of a young athlete to participate in a particular competition. In the structure of mobilization readiness, there are: features of the characteristics of attention before a responsible performance and such a duration of concentration of attention that provides the most effective performance. The duration of concentration of attention is determined by the need to: free yourself for some time from the influence of interfering stimuli; achieve an optimal emotional state, reduce excessive tension; bring the idea of upcoming actions to maximum brightness and accuracy. The latter is the most important moment in the process of concentration, determining the state of mobilization readiness and prompting the beginning of action.

To regulate the mental state of a young athlete before going to the start, a mental representation of the program of the upcoming performance is of great importance, which should lift the mood, eliminate stiffness, relax the muscles.

There are two groups of techniques for managing your actions. The 1st category includes: self-distraction from the process of activity, its switching to

technique, muscle relaxation, breathing, the opponent. The 2nd group includes: self-complacency at the level of a certain self-mobilization (thoughts about "free" non-strenuous work, about reducing excitement), self-control (thoughts backed up by self-confidence), self-persuasion (reasoned proof to oneself of the possibilities of solving general and particular competitive tasks), self-evidence (categorical instructions to oneself about immediate fulfillment the task at hand, about overcoming oneself).

Coaches need to disclose the specifics of the psychological compatibility of the students, the recruitment of the team, taking into account the personal qualities of the players. Along with this, the psychologist gives recommendations on the results of direct work with athletes, which significantly help in preparing for competitions.

Direct work with young athletes is based on the study of their individual and personal characteristics. Most often, this information can be obtained using survey research methods, observation, as well as testing, i.e. through the use of psychological diagnostics. The data obtained, along with the development of recommendations for coaches, are used in preparation for individual consultations with athletes. At the same time, diagnostics can be aimed not only at studying the individual characteristics of players, but also at studying intra-group processes in the team as a whole. It is necessary to measure the prevailing psychological climate in the group, the sociometric structure of the sports team, etc. Studies show that the use of psychological diagnostics alone is not enough for full-fledged psychological work with athletes.

The coach should, for example, organize the training process in such a way as to cause young athletes "game hunger", contribute to the preservation of their nervous and playing potential and prevent neurotic reactions of satiety (this method can be used in teams whose players have a good command of the tactical and technical arsenal, are sufficiently prepared physically and for a long time time to play together).

In order to reduce the pre-start tension of young athletes, the coach can organize "unloading" days free from classes in "his" sport. On this day, you can visit the pool, hold cross-country, outdoor games, etc.

The measures protecting young athletes from the effects of irritants that can cause negative emotions in the pre-competition period include: determining the composition of the team long before the competition (this calms young athletes who doubt their abilities, and also eliminates the spirit of unhealthy rivalry in the team); the absence of a strict separation of players into main and reserve (this allows everyone for a young athlete to feel like a full-fledged member of the team); meetings at which teenagers are criticized by the coach and teammates; conversations during which the advantage of the team in comparison with other

teams is explained, taking into account the factors of stimulating psychological impact (for example, the support of their fans).

The role of the coach is also responsible during the competition. The match begins with a game setup, during which the coach gives a detailed assessment of the future opponent and sets game tactical tasks for the team, as well as individual tasks for individual players. It is most advisable to carry out the installation on the day of the game 2-3 hours before it starts, so that young athletes can comprehend the team and individual task and find out all the unclear issues. If the installation is carried out on the eve of the competition, then many teenagers will mentally "lose" the situations of the upcoming game, which can cause them neurotic reactions of anxious expectation. In 20-30 minutes. before entering the sports field, the coach must repeat the main tasks in the upcoming game and, through psychological influence, adjust the athletes to the game. During the break, the coach's instructions should be concise, but at the same time authoritarian.

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